

MS26 Review of participation in RCOF events and engagement with National Met Services, summarise progress to date and ongoing strategy

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* **R**=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other
 ** **PU**=Public, **CO**=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), **CI**=Classified

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Executive Summary

ASPECT aims to deliver actionable, high-resolution climate predictions integrated into decision-making processes and tailored to the needs of the climate adaptation community. Through collaboration with National Meteorological Services (NMSs) and participation in WMO's Regional Climate Outlook Forums (RCOFs), ASPECT fosters the exchange of ideas and strengthens the usability of its outputs, which is the concern of all WPs.

A two-day online workshop for NMSs “*From Seasons to Decades: Seamless Prediction for a Better Future*” (October 22-23, 2024) brought together representatives from RCOFs, NMSs, and international organizations. The workshop focused on seasonal-to-decadal predictions, predictability research, and user needs. By establishing direct communication channels with NMSs, it set the foundation for scaling up ASPECT's climate information. WP7 was technical organizer of the event, while other WPs 1-6 actively contributed in designing the sessions, selecting speakers and panelists, and creating discussion topics.

ASPECT plans to further engage with NMSs to integrate its advancements into operational workflows. The project will also disseminate knowledge through training programs, leveraging existing platforms and creating accessible educational materials. Collaboration with the WMO and RCOFs will further enhance dissemination efforts and support the development of regional and decadal climate products.

About ASPECT

ASPECT aims to set up and demonstrate a seamless climate information (SCI) system with a time horizon up to 30 years and accompanied with underlying research and using climate information for sectoral applications. The project's goal is to improve existing climate prediction systems and to merge their outputs across timescales together with climate projections to unify a SCI as a standard for sectoral decision-making.

The project focus will be on European climate information, but we will also look where there is a wider policy interest (e.g., disaster preparedness) and in regions of European interest. We will maintain a strong link with the WCRP lighthouse activities to exploit learning for explaining and predicting earth system change. To provide a bandwidth diversity of information, the SCI system will be based on multi-model climate forecasts and will build on learning from projects such as EUCP. It will align with new activities on Digital Twins within Europe, including DestinE. The SCI will combine physical science aspects with those from other disciplines to ensure the information is robust, reliable, and relevant for a range of user-driven decision cases. The information package will incorporate baseline forecasts and projections (plus uncertainty), and will explore new frontiers (e.g., extremes which are of socioeconomic high-level interest).

To ensure success, the research will encompass: an understanding and attribution of various processes along timescales (such as exploring signal-to-noise ratio) and their impact on predictability, new ways of initialisation of the prediction systems, merging predictions with projections, provision of regional SCI for Europe by downscaling (statistical methods, AI) and HighRes models (including convection-permitting models) and innovative post-processing method enhancing the skill and robustness of the climate forecasts.

1. Project objectives and aims

ASPECT aims to create actionable, high-resolution climate predictions, accessible to adaptation practitioners and integrated into decision-making processes. ASPECT also aims to strengthen collaborations with and within the climate adaptation community, by addressing their information needs and ensuring project outputs are useful and usable. All these efforts are and will be shaped with climate prediction specialists through engagement with National Meteorological Services (NMSs) and by active participation in WMO's Regional Climate Outlook Forums (RCOFs).

ASPECT already has in its consortium several NMSs as partners (UK Met Office, SMHI, RHMZ) or as members of the project's external international advisory board (DWD). The project also aims to work closely with up to 10 additional national services across Europe.

Engaging with NMSs will:

- inform the WPs1-3 on user needs and challenges,
- complement the Super Users in WP4,
- supplement information gained during User Forums in WP5,
- help upscaling activities in WP5,
- inform the design of workflows and applications developed by WP6,
- help further uptake of ASPECT outputs and exploitation activities in WP7,
- and most important, enable lasting impact of the ASPECT project.

Additionally, participation in RCOFs serves as a channel for disseminating new climate prediction data to local and regional forecasters, as well as engaged users.

2. Engagement with National Meteorological Services

2.1. Regional climate outlook forums (RCOFs)

Regional Climate Outlook Forums (RCOFs) was initiated by the World Meteorological Organization, in the late 1990s, in order to bring together national, regional and international climate experts, and with the aim to provide consensus based climate prediction for the upcoming season of summer or winter¹.

Such regional forums have spread to many regions across the world (Figure 1). In Europe, there are two RCOFs: South East European Climate Outlook Forum (SEECOF) and Mediterranean Climate Outlook Forum (MedCOF). MedCOF area integrates already existing COF areas in the Mediterranean region, PRESANORD (RCOF for North Africa) and SEECOF, as well as Western European and Middle Eastern Mediterranean countries. SEECOF closely collaborates with MedCOF in order to harmonize the climate outlook statement.

¹ <https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/climate-services/regional-climate-outlook-forums>

The core concept of all the RCOFs is delivering consensus based climate outlook products to end users. Afterwards, the created products for the region are tailored to meet the local conditions and disseminated by each National Meteorological Service (NMSs).

At the beginning, users from different state authorities and economy sectors (forestry, agriculture, insurance, electric power companies and water management) were participants of the SEECOF meetings. Unfortunately, due to lack of funding and Covid-19 restrictions, face-2-face meetings ceased, and communication among SEECOF climate experts continued via Forum only. On the other hand, MedCOF, as a user section, organises training workshops on seasonal climate prediction to strengthen the capacity of the operational climate forecasters.

At the beginning of the ASPECT project, participants of the SEECOF and MedCOF are informed about the project, and later invited to participate in User Forums and Workshop for NMSs. Since the activities in the SEECOF are conducted online in the form of a forum, a separate section was created in order to inform participants on the objectives of the project. SEECOF forum will be used during the project to share invitations to the ASPECT User Forums and to disseminate project results.

2.2. Dissemination through the networks

Besides RCOFs, communication is also established with the EUMETNET network of European NMSs.

EUMETNET was established in 2009 as an association with a primary mission to help cooperation and collaboration among its members and to represent them externally on a collective basis, particularly when communicating with European organizations, especially the EU and EC. The focus of cooperation between members has been on the core capabilities of the members, in particular: observing systems, data processing, basic forecasting products, research and development, training, coordination of technical assistance, and production of essential output information to end-users – especially the citizens of Europe.

As for the RCOFs, participants of the EUMETNET Climate Expert Team (CET) and Heads of Climate (HoC) are informed about the project, and invited to participate in User Forums and Workshop for NMSs. For the Workshop, connections were established with the EUMETNET Numerical Weather Prediction and Climate Scenarios teams as well.

Besides EUMETNET and RCOFs officially defined networks, information on ASPECT is disseminated directly through personal contacts.

2.3. Survey user needs

During the preparation of the Deliverable 5.1 *“Rapid assessment of climate information user needs”*², in order to supplement limited literature information on climate information use and unmet needs, WP5 prepared the mini-questionnaire for the European NMSs. The survey, along with the questions, provided

² https://www.aspect-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/aspect_d5.1_rapid_assessment_of_climate_information_user_needs.pdf

a summary of preliminary ASPECT project activities. This provided insights into the production and perceived use of seasonal and interannual climate predictions (Figure 2).

An online mini-questionnaire was shared in March 2023, through the SEECOF and EUMETNET-CET networks as well as an informal network of the contacts of the ASPECT project partners. The survey consisted of 17 short-answer questions regarding the production, dissemination, data source, usability of seasonal and interannual climate forecasts in Europe. The mini-questionnaire was answered by 31 individuals from 16 different European NMSs. Detailed summary of the results can be found in the Deliverable 5.1.

Figure 2 Map of seasonal (left) and interannual (right) climate forecast production and availability in Europe as per responses from NMSs.

3. Workshop for NMSs

3.1. Background

Engagement with NMSs offers one of the best routes to further development and uptake of ASPECT outputs. Live and open discussions between data providers and users, both from ASPECT and NMSs, grant exchange of ideas, experiences and needs.

Initial plan was that ASPECT partners participate in the RCOFs meetings in the region (SEECOF and MedCOF) and gain experience to be shared with the World Meteorological Organization to transpose the lessons learned to the set of RCOFs it coordinates. Due to changes that organization of RCOFs experienced in recent years³, ASPECT project decided to organise one event that will gather representatives of RCOFs operating in Europe region and beyond (SEECOF, MedCOF, NEACOF⁴,

³ SEECOF and MedCOF are at the moment online events dedicated to issuing consensus seasonal forecasts and its verification. Side events for promotion of projects and engagement with users are on hold, but hopefully will be revived again soon.

⁴ NEACOF - North Eurasian Climate Outlook Forum coordinated by NEACC (North Eurasian Climate Center) encompassing the area of North Eurasia - territory of the CIS (Commonwealth of independent States) countries. More information regarding NEACOF sessions can be found here: <https://seakc.meteoinfo.ru/en/neacof>

PRESANORD), WMO, regional climate centers and other organizations; in general national meteorological services from Europe and beyond.

The goal of this workshop was to establish more direct communication between ASPECT and NMSs, to showcase ASPECT research and get their feedback, as well as to start creating a channel for disseminating new climate prediction data to local and regional climate forecasters. It also set the ground for the further activities in upscaling of climate information created in ASPECT as well as exploitation activities.

The Workshop was organised as a two day on-line event, 22-23. October 2024, each day lasting 2.5 hours. The official name of the Workshop was “From Seasons To Decades: Seamless Prediction for a Better Future”.

WP7 was technical organizer of the event, while other WPs 1-6 actively contributed in designing the sessions, selecting the speakers and panelists, and creating discussion topics.

In selecting the speakers and roundtables panelists, special attention was given to ensuring gender and geographical diversity (Table 1). Unfortunately, gender balance was not achieved for the round table in Session 1 on seasonal-to-decadal (S2D) predictions, which may reflect a gender imbalance in producing climate predictions, particularly within NMSs. Another challenge was achieving geographical diversity among NMSs speakers and panelists. This may be due to underdeveloped parts of climate services (CS) within NMSs in Eastern Europe (the delivery chain from climate predictions to end-user products) or to insufficient international promotion of these climate services, which left the organizing team unaware of potential participants.

Table 1 Gender and geographical distribution of speakers and panelist

	Number of female speakers and panelists	Number of male speakers and panelists	Number of countries represented among speakers and panelists
Session 1	2	6	6
Session 2	3	3	5
Session 3	3	2	4

3.2. Dissemination of the call

Since the Workshop is dedicated only for the NMSs, the call for participation is mainly distributed through different networks of NMSs as well as personal and project partners contacts. More than 235 persons were contacted directly, and 6 networks who further disseminated the call to their participants. At first, the call was disseminated to contacts in Europe, Middle East and North Africa (participants of the SEECOF and MedCOF), but later on the call was circulated without geographical restrictions.

For the promotion of the Workshop and dissemination activities, WP7 created a leaflet with the Agenda (Appendix I). Invitation letter is given in Appendix II.

The Workshop was promoted on social media, ASPECT Newsletter and web page. Although promotion tools did not include a link to the registration form, email was provided so that interested parties could contact the dedicated project team to express their interest (Figure 3 Advertisement of the Workshop on the X social media. Figure 3). The call on X platform was posted several times with a maximum number of 106 views.

Figure 3 Advertisement of the Workshop on the X social media.

3.3. Sessions

Event had three sessions covering the following topics:

- 1) Seasonal to Decadal Predictions,
- 2) Predictability and Novel Approaches, and
- 3) User Needs.

In all sessions the set of presentations were followed by a round table and discussion. All presenters of the Sessions were invited to participate in the discussions as well.

The first day and first session was focused on production and provision of operational and innovative seasonal-to-decadal predictions. At the beginning, the MetOffice and DWD, as two NMSs which are global producing centers within the WMO Centre for Annual-to-Decadal Climate Prediction, presented their work. After presentations of operational practices, ASPECT presented new modeling systems and experiments and how these data can be accessed (work achieved in WP1 and WP6).

The second day, Sessions 2 and 3, was dedicated to predictability, research and user needs. The Session 2 started with a presentation of the MeteoFrance which is a lead node for Long Range Forecast (LRF) within the WMO network of Regional Climate Centers (RCC) for Europe (Regional Association VI, RA VI), in short RA-VI RCC-LRF node. Afterwards ASPECT presented its up-to-date research conducted in WPs 2 and 3 on predictability, downscaling, time merging etc. The second session of day two was dedicated to user needs and efforts in WPs 4 and 5.

Sessions were moderated by project partners: BSC (Albert Soret and Markus Donat), RHMZ (Aleksandra Kržič), and the UK MetOffice (Freya Gerry). Technical hosts of the event were Aleksandra Kržič (RHMZ) and Andria Nicodemou (BSC).

The Workshop started with the introduction to the ASPECT project. Coordinator of the ASPECT project Albert Soret gave an overview of motivations and research gaps addressed by ASPECT, projects' objectives and achievements.

As a reaction to an introductory presentation of the ASPECT project, a representative of the WMO was interested to find out *“How can we access the forecast and prediction products to link it to our users from the broader UN system?”*.

While many of the products mentioned in the introduction of the ASPECT are not yet operational, transitioning them into operations depends on the support of the European NMSs and ECMWF. If they are ready to make them operational, the community can help to include them in the WMO Integrated Processing and Prediction System (WIPPS).

Success also depends on understanding predictions performance (skill) and relevance to user decision-making, including their economic value. To address this, ASPECT is engaging users to evaluate climate services, not just through statistical measures but by assessing the impact of decisions based on these predictions.

3.3.1. Session 1: Seasonal to Decadal Predictions

The first Session of the workshop was dedicated to production and provision of S2D predictions.

3.3.1.1. Presentations

The first two presentations gave insights in operational practice and research and development activities in two NMSs that are Global Producing Centers for S2D predictions within WMO, the MetOffice and DWD.

Leon Hermanson, an Expert Scientist in the Met Office and Leader of the Lead Centre for Annual-to-Decadal Climate Prediction within WMO, gave a flavor of what his research group is doing in the area of seasonal to decadal predictions in the Met Office as well as outline of the Lead Center. In the following, Kristina Fröhlich, a Senior Scientist developing and producing climate predictions at DWD, gave a short overview of DWDclimate predictions performances, focusing on model and system configurations and on what they are aiming for in the next few years.

After the presentations of activities of those two NMSs, the ASPECT project presented novel configurations of prediction systems for seamless climate information and its data management. Magdalena Alonso Balmaseda, Head of Earth System Predictability at ECMWF, introduced new protocols to provide climate information and the idea to bridge the gap between seasonal and decadal predictions and between decadal predictions and climate projections. The efforts ASPECT is making to comply with the data FAIR principles, the challenges of working with different archiving infrastructures, encoding guidelines and data documentation, were demonstrated by Charalampos Karvelis, data management engineer at ECMWF.

3.3.1.2. Roundtable & Discussion

The presentations were followed by a round table and discussion. The round table was comprised of representatives of global producing and contributing centers for annual to decadal predictions from Europe:

- Francisco Doblás-Reyes, Director of Earth Sciences Department in BSC
Coordinator of the Climateurope2 project (standardisation of climate services), lead of the Destination Earth Digital Twin for Climate Adaptation at the BSC and author of the IPCC AR5 and AR6;
- Pasha Karami, Climate Researcher at SMHI
Investigating the interannual and interdecadal climate variability processes for better representation of future climate;
- Dario Nicolì, Climate Researcher at CMCC
Responsible for operational multiannual to multidecadal predictions;
- Esteban Rodríguez Guisado, Head of Climate Evaluation and Modelling at AEMET
Provides downscaled projections, operational seasonal forecasting and climate services for Spain, and MedCOF coordinator.

Before the start of the round table a link to short menti (and a questionnaire later) was shared in order to survey the audience on how interested are they in the seasonal and decadal time scales, does the S2D predictions meet their needs, what they want to be improved and how interested are they in the new proposed ASPECT protocols. Results of this menti and the questionnaire shared at the end of both days were meant to feed in the WP1's *'MS2 Completion of second round of consultation on proposed user-relevant enhancements to seasonal-to-decadal dataset for testing and benchmarking'*. Both menti and questionnaire were prepared by WP1 and WP6.

The discussion addressed various aspects of using climate predictions and projections to improve adaptation to climate change, as well as the challenges and opportunities associated with their implementation. These might be summarised as in the following.

There are several points of view on why there is a more uptake of climate projections than initialised predictions.

This might be due to the fact that climate projections have been developed and refined over decades, resulting in accessible products like threshold exceedances, extreme event forecasts, and climate indices. This abundance of indicators makes them more practical for public use. The climate projection community has benefitted from decades of coordinated multimodal experiments, creating a standardized framework. In contrast, initialized predictions are newer and less established. They are also more complex, requiring advanced expertise to interpret.

The other explanation could be legal bindings. National adaptation plans often mandate the use of climate projections for many different sectors.

The opposite view is that users are often unaware of the existence of initialized predictions or do not understand them well enough. Users, particularly in the private sector, often prioritize shorter time horizons (1-5 years) and remain confused about whether initialized predictions are superior or complementary to projections. Insufficient communication and misalignment between user needs and available data further burden their broader application. Additionally, the inertia within the scientific and user communities favors projections, as they are familiar, easy to access, and useful for training and research.

The discussion explored further whether the value of initial predictions has increased since we now see effects of climate change. Panellists think that the value and the demand for climate predictions has increased.

Historically, people are used to certain climate distributions, helping to guide activities within expected norms. However, with climate change causing frequent and unprecedented extremes, predictions now have a critical role in assessing the likelihood of new, unusual events that lie outside historical expectations. The importance of climate predictions lies not only in anticipating extremes but also in providing a clearer understanding of the broader distribution of climate conditions over time.

Event attribution, understanding the causes behind specific extreme events, is the most relevant part of the attribution problem. It is more credible if conducted using the same initialized models rather than models used for climate projections. There were European projects in the FP7 and Horizon 2020 as well as some research institutions that included this concept in its activities.

Initialized simulations can also help verify critical changes in Earth components. For example, they may offer insights into the Arctic sea ice disappearance or shifts in the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). Initialised predictions are likely to better capture variability providing a clearer picture of changes over the next 10–20 years.

Climate information should be tailored to answer specific questions posed by users. Users are less concerned with the source of the data, whether it comes from predictions, projections, or attribution studies. Instead, they prioritize credibility, clarity, and relevance to their decision-making needs.

Some additional views were given on the specific scientific, technical and also societal aspects that need to be improved to increase the use of climate predictions.

While private companies are advancing AI models for weather and climate predictions, they often stop after data provision because scaling is complex and costly. Here the role of NMSs is essential but the question is whether there is enough human resources and capabilities. Unlike traditional meteorology, where formal training programs exist, there is a lack of equivalent education for interpreting and communicating seasonal and climate predictions. In addition, increased collaboration between NMSs is needed to share resources, libraries, and expertise.

Sustained engagement with users is essential but resource-intensive, especially for NMSs with limited capacity. Many services and tools are initially developed as research prototypes under time-bound funding. Transitioning these into stable, operational systems after project funding ends is always a challenge. Creating frameworks to channel user interactions and maintain services long-term is critical. Collaboration among NMSs on overlapping topics and developments could be beneficial.

Users may not always articulate clear requirements at first. Existing tools and visualizations, such as climate atlases, can help identify gaps and trigger discussions for more tailored solutions.

The lack of operationalization for climate projections within the WMO context poses a challenge, as adequate funding to sustain current activities is lacking. This is now part of the discussions within CMIP. At the same time, the Climateurope2 project is discussing what does it mean that the user interaction is complicated and what the implications are for the market (actors that play a role in delivering services) itself. Actors like C3S are absolutely necessary. C3S positioned themselves in the climate services market for adaptation and increasingly will be the case for mitigation. Beyond that, it's very difficult to identify a profitable market for the delivery of climate related services. This is a problem because that means that we don't have a pooling mechanism that can make the problem more visible. Also there is no mechanism to provide resources to the NMSs that can provide a channel for the developments in research to make their way into society.

The importance of defining data standards to facilitate uptake of climate services was pointed out as well.

3.3.1.3. Feedback from the audience

Audience wanted to know a little bit more on the German ICON-XPP model. The model will be released to the broader community soon, and it is currently tested for issuing seasonal and decadal forecasts. There were several questions related to the DWD model developments in the chat, whether DWD is producing the statistical downscaling on the DWD model, or are targeting the complete C3S; does DWD

downscale other essential climate variables apart from temperature and precipitation? At the moment DWD is doing statistical downscaling only on their model, but the plan is to develop a multi-model ensemble. Downscaling is done for at least 8 variables over Germany, for an input for impact models, especially for hydrological models.

After the presentation of the “Novel prediction system for seamless climate information” developed by ASPECT, several questions were raised in chat and live.

There was a discussion on subseasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) predictions, emphasizing their importance for Climate Watch Advisories. While S2S forecasts (from weeks to one or two months ahead) are not directly addressed by ASPECT, they are seen as a critical gap to bridge, and ECMWF is working to improve them. These forecasts, now issued daily with 100 ensemble members, were previously issued twice a week with only 50 members. There is ongoing work to make S2S data publicly available (not just maps) in real time, with the WMO Lead Centre for sub-seasonal forecasts playing a key role in data dissemination. In the context of future projects, there was a proposal for further research to bridge the gap between sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, potentially through EU-funded initiatives.

The discussion also touched on the challenge of correcting errors related to trend biases in forecasts. It appears that these errors are difficult to correct due to complex model physics, particularly in the tropics, and long-standing deficiencies. While the ideal solution is to address these issues at their source, calibration is used as an interim measure.

The importance of acknowledging model deficiencies and addressing them in the context of ASPECT was highlighted. Some of the errors or its sources are such that the errors cannot be completely or usefully corrected by post-processing. Additionally, the errors in trends compromise the ability to make predictions that are useful in the current climate. Decadal predictions share the same problems as seasonal predictions as well as projections. The difficulty in solving these issues, due to limited understanding of atmospheric physics, clouds, convections, impacts of aerosols, is noted.

There were some reactions to the Discussion in the chat.

The UNSEEN (Unprecedented Simulated Extremes using Ensembles) project focuses on resilience to current climate changes and variability, which differs from the use of long-term projections. The added value of initialized forecasts lies in enabling users who rely on long-term projections to assess whether new decadal forecasts provide additional information that might impact their decisions. Users interested in the current climate or variability over the next five years often lack tailored information or experts to help them develop the required climate data, even from existing projections.

Maintaining even successful prototypes requires significant effort, which is often overlooked. Effective use of climate predictions requires extensive interaction, training, and patience from users, especially when the benefits are marginal compared to other sources of information. That is one of the reasons why the operationalization of climate projections is now under discussion.

Recently, users in Bulgaria have shown interest in drought forecasts on timescales of up to two years ahead to support decision-making for addressing the current drought. This new demand is partly driven

by the availability of the latest decadal forecasts online, but users' expectations often exceed the actual skill of these forecasts.

There were also questions from the ASPECT for the audience, whether they can formulate what level of additional skill or performance they would need to guide their decisions based on decadal predictions rather than on projections?

The discussion highlighted the importance of assessing the value derived from initialization in climate predictions, as suggested by studies like Smith et al. (2019)⁵. Ideally, such assessments should be conducted annually for each initialization, but this process can be challenging for users. There's curiosity about whether the methodology from Smith et al. is consistently applied to each decadal forecast.

One perspective suggests that instead of focusing solely on forecast skill, discussions should center on the value these predictions bring, such as the benefit of more frequent updates on long-term climate outlooks without waiting for the next CMIP.

However, there's also a question about whether the relatively modest added value from initialization is sufficient for improved decision-making. In cases where the added value of initialized predictions is limited, co-production with users can play a significant role. Collaborating with users to provide context-specific information can enhance the perceived usefulness of predictions. Often, users place higher value on the effort to support them in navigating climate information than on the actual quality of forecasts. This co-productive approach not only meets users' needs but also enriches decision-making processes.

Project partners were keen to hear of examples from users where the additional information from e.g. initialised decadal predictions had an impact on their decisions that would otherwise be purely based on non-initialised projections. One response was provided:

"I was involved in a hackathon a couple of years ago where a user was interested in using decadal predictions of wind speed to inform decisions about where to locate offshore wind turbines over the next decades to maximise wind power generation. I think, however, it was concluded that the decadal forecast for wind speed did not have skill in the region they were interested in, so they just used climatology. I wonder if there would have been something they could do to explore the value of the decadal prediction in their case" (ASPECT Workshop participant).

⁵ : Smith, D. M.;Eade, R.;Scaife, A. A.;Caron, L.-P.;Danabasoglu, G.;DelSole, T. M.;Delworth, T.;Doblas-Reyes, F. J.;Dunstone, N. J.;Hermanson, L.;Kharin, V.;Kimoto, M.;Merryfield, W. J.;Mochizuki, T.;Müller, W. A.;Pohlmann, H.;Yeager, S.;Yang, X.; 2019: Robust skill of decadal climate predictions. *Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 2 (13), DOI : <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41612-019-0071-y>

3.3.2. Session 2: Predictability and Novel Approaches

The second Session was focused on current multi-system predictions and the added value of initialization, as well as the latest methods for temporal merging and downscaling, designed to deliver high-resolution, user-specific information across multiple time scales.

3.3.2.1. Presentations

Lauriane Batté, Head of the Climate Analysis and Seasonal Forecasting Department at the Climatology and Climate Services Directorate at Météo-France, gave an outline of current practice in seasonal forecasting as RCC node in RA-VI region, its limitations and challenges, and some examples of research to operations activities at Meteo-France.

Afterwards, Holger Pohlmann, Research Scientist in the Earth System Modeling and Prediction group of the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology presented some examples of good skill from ASPECT, particularly regarding Europe, related to the available innovative predictions and highlighted the added value of initialization while also addressing their limitations, such as unrealistic extremes and the signal-to-noise issue.

An overview of temporal merging methods and downscaling approaches carried out in ASPECT, aiming to provide user specific information combined across time scales and in high-resolution was presented by Beena Balan Sarojini, Climate Researcher at University of Oxford.

3.3.2.2. Roundtable & Discussion

Round table afterwards gathered presenters as well representatives of NMSs:

- Clementine Dalelane, Mathematician at the Climate Department of DWD
Working at statistical subsampling of seasonal forecasts, multidecadal forecasts, quality assessment of climate projections, ensemble selection of climate projections, bias adjustment;
- Philip Lorenz, Meteorologist in the Climate and Environment Department of DWD
His work focuses on empirical statistical downscaling and attribution research
(Unfortunately due to personal issues Mr Lorenz couldn't participate in the Workshop);
- Ramon Fuentes-Franco, Climate Researcher at the Rossby Centre in SMHI
His research interests are climate modes of variability and sources of predictability at interannual scales. He currently develops machine learning methods for improving seasonal forecasts and the detection of extreme events,

in joint discussion on the challenges and potential advancements in downscaling and improving seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions, particularly in the context of large-scale modes of variability and their connection to regional applications. Summary of the discussion is provided below.

Downscaling is important for tailoring climate predictions for high-resolution applications demanded by users, such as agriculture. Global climate models generally capture the large-scale signals but struggle with smaller-scale details, which are often required by users.

Teleconnections, like the link between tropical Pacific variability and Scandinavian precipitation, are foundational for predictions. However, global warming may alter these patterns, making it harder to rely on historical relationships. For example, 2023 was predicted to have a dry summer in northern Europe, but unexpected shifts in large-scale signal in late summer reversed this trend, highlighting the difficulty in using observed teleconnections and modes of variability for future predictions. A key challenge is also that models often fail to replicate the observed variability accurately.

There are model issues with representing key processes and teleconnections as well as model biases that lead to the small predictable signals. It is necessary to address model deficiencies, such as signal-to-noise issues and the ratio of predictable components of the geopotential field. In regions like the North Atlantic and Europe, the signal-to-noise ratio remains problematic, particularly in winter, where forecasts appear more chaotic than reality. Additionally, the potential predictability, which is present in nature, is not fully utilized by the models. This can be seen in a wide diversity in circulation patterns in the seasonal predictions, which results later into a very small variance in the predicted signal and also a very low predictive scale.

Many efforts are made to enhance predictability. For example, subsampling ensemble members based on statistically predicted circulation indices has shown promise, particularly in winter when the ratio of predictive components over Europe is more favorable. However, these methods are less effective in summer due to stronger local processes, such as convection.

The problem that also diminishes the predictive skill of the seasonal forecast is that the bias is usually non-stationary in circulation patterns, it varies conditional to circulation patterns. Current bias correction methods rely on climatology, and these methods don't eliminate the bias completely. That is why more advanced techniques, including machine learning, are being explored to address non-stationary biases. Analog downscaling methods using large-scale parameters of the seasonal forecast could improve its predictive skill if biases in circulation patterns are corrected rigorously across spatial and temporal dimensions.

Machine learning is generally considered a promising tool for bias correction and generating high-resolution predictions. But limited data availability, especially on pressure levels, limit the training and testing of advanced methods. Larger datasets are needed for robust validation of these techniques, particularly as climate change introduces additional complexities.

Seamless prediction, integrating seasonal and decadal timescales into a continuous framework, is gaining more attention. This approach provides a single, user-friendly time series and unified data for decision-making across varying time horizons (e.g., weeks to years). ASPECT encourages co-production with users to tailor predictions to specific needs, maximizing the utility of probabilistic information even when forecast skill is limited. Additionally ASPECT is working on bridging the gap between seasonal and decadal predictions through more frequent updates and overlapping prediction systems.

3.3.2.3. Feedback from the audience

One of the participants was curious about whether MeteoFrance includes the clustering analysis in verification bulletins, and have considered computing variability patterns, weather regimes and other analysis related products represented by cluster? MeteoFrance worked on weather regimes and projections onto variability patterns associated with the clusters as well as plot the composites of atmospheric circulation in the analysis.

Additionally, a suggestion for research was given. It would be interesting to see if it is possible to identify weather regimes or larger scale modes of variability associated with an increase in extreme rainfall from convective events.

Parallel to discussion, participants shared their thoughts on discussion questions in the chat.

The potential for improving downscaling techniques largely depends on the quality, resolution, and length of observational data available for training and calibration. High-quality observational data is crucial not only for downscaling but also for calibration and assessing the overall forecast quality. For statistical downscaling limited availability of variables, such as those on pressure levels, restrict the application of more complex techniques.

One significant challenge is the limited number of cases available for testing different methods, particularly on seasonal and decadal timescales. Issues related to conditional bias and circulation-dependent bias, as well as more advanced methods require larger datasets to ensure robustness. And with climate change, these challenges are becoming increasingly complex. Testing methods with limited initialization dates makes it difficult to evaluate their performance, even on hindcast data sets and applying them in real-time. Adding to this, feedback on the efficiency of these methods also takes time.

The role of teleconnections varies by timescale, and the source of predictability may differ accordingly. While models often perform well with ENSO, other modes of variability and their interactions within models remain areas of interest.

3.3.3. Session 3: User Needs

Collaborative case studies were presented in Session 3 to showcase the power of tailored climate information in supporting better-informed adaptation decisions. We also went beyond individual case studies and explored user needs as well as the drivers of climate risk management and climate information use in Europe.

3.3.3.1. Presentations

Session 3 started with two ASPECT presentations on the user engagement conducted in the ASPECT.

Verónica Torralba, Researcher at BSC, presented ASPECT co-developing case studies exploring how we can provide fit-for-purpose climate information for decision making. These case studies are the result of collaboration with 5 "Super Users" from various societally important sectors, including agriculture, finance, humanitarian and governance. Their involvement allows for the evaluation of the usability, socio-economic benefits, and added value of seamless climate information, ultimately enhancing its effectiveness in supporting adaptation efforts.

The next talk was given by Suraje Dessai, Professor of Climate Change Adaptation at the Sustainability Research Institute in the School of Earth and Environment at the University of Leeds. He explained how the ASPECT project explored user needs across society as well as the drivers of climate risk management and climate information use in Europe.

3.3.3.2. Roundtable & Discussion

Round table and discussion part of Session 3 followed the presentations. Participants of the round table were:

- Ralf Döscher, Head of Regional Climate Research at Rossby Centre in SMHI
The group works on process chains towards climate services, downscaling of climate data, climate impacts and climate communication;
- Amelie Hoff, Research Scientist at DWD
Works on user-orientated products for sub-seasonal to decadal forecasts and is involved in projects in the field of climate prediction. She is also responsible for the development and maintenance of the seasonal post-processing system at DWD for the German region.
- Freya Gerry, Senior Scientist in the Climate Resilience Team at the Met Office
Working to improve the inclusion of state-of-the-art climate science into useful and useable climate service prototypes

Speakers also joined the group discussions on the use, communication, and potential of climate prediction and projection data in various sectors, particularly for decision-making and adaptation planning.

The discussion has brought up that many users struggle to differentiate between interannual climate predictions and long-term projections highlighting the need for clearer communication and education.

Projections, based on global climate models like CMIP, are more widely available and understood, whereas climate predictions are less accessible and often misunderstood despite their potential value.

Delays in updating downscaled climate data pose challenges for users needing real-time and high-resolution information. They are also asking for information on extreme events, sector specific indicators, and even information on timescales of several hundred years.

Users vary in their use of climate data, some use raw data, while others prefer digested forms like visual summaries or other digested type of information. There is also a very large range of users' expertise and interest, so ASPECT distinguished two groups in terms of terminology, a community of practice of users who are actually using the information themselves and a community of interest of users who are not necessarily using the prediction information directly by themselves at the moment.

Some of the examples of how prediction and projection information is leading to tangible benefits and improved outcomes through the provision of very user-focused services were highlighted. A lot of NMSs are tailored towards climate information from projections. One example is the climate service from the Met Office that has been produced to provide local authorities with the information about extremes. Local authority can at the click of a button get a report to download, e.g. the service is tailored towards government decision makers who don't want to do any data analysis. In Sweden, a similar climate service exists. Service is based on regionalization of climate projections and most of the customers are local authorities.

Additional sector-specific examples of climate services are provided during the discussion:

- In agriculture, frost days are defined by temperature thresholds, but humidity and seasonal timing also play a role. This highlights the importance of co-production with users to refine relevant indicators.
- For urban planning and infrastructure, long-term projections (~30 years) are critical for investments in climate adaptation in flood prone zones, building new parts of the cities, transportation planning and in coastal protection, as some of the illustrations.
- Energy sectors, like wind and hydropower, benefit from tailored indicators (e.g., icing on wind turbines, frequency of events with high humidity, days with temperatures close to zero, streamflow forecasts etc.).
- In forestry, projections guide tree planting for future climates (for the next 30-50 up to 80 years), while shorter-term predictions (months and years ahead) aid in operational decisions. They are not using seasonal and decadal information yet due to issues with availability and skill.
- For groundwater management in Germany, Federal Institute uses DWD predictions and projections to operate a groundwater level prediction system, showcasing a collaborative model for delivering actionable data.

Challenges in communication are also highlighted. In the light of seamless predictions it will be a communication challenge because it is a new technology and people need to get used to it and start thinking how to use it. Transparent communication of prediction skill, which is a key concern for users, is crucial. Germany uses a traffic light system (green, yellow, red) to visually and intuitively communicate prediction skill. This approach has increased trust and proper use of the data. DWD also organises yearly user workshops and individual meetings in order to gather user feedback and educate their users.

Users accustomed to deterministic data face challenges in adopting probabilistic forecasts. Thus, collaboration is necessary to develop decision-making frameworks that integrate these forecasts effectively. Additionally, translating predictions into tangible value (e.g., economic savings) can drive adoption and trust in climate services. Probabilistic data must be framed within the cost-benefit contexts of various sectors to maximize its impact.

New technologies, like AI and Machine Learning, can complement traditional methods, enhancing the resolution and timeliness of climate services. Classical methods cannot be abandoned. The AI needs to learn from what the classical methods are doing since there is no other data for training the models. AI can also improve downscaling processes and focus on extreme weather events to meet specific user needs.

Interactive, continuous engagement with users fosters mutual learning. In this way users gain understanding of probabilistic forecasts, while providers learn about specific sectoral needs, which all helps tailor products to users unique needs. Within activities in RCOFs, capacity building, interaction with users and training and workshops are parts that RCOFs are trying to implement.

3.3.3.3. Feedback from the audience

In the chat, it is highlighted again that workshops and opportunities for interaction are essential. In addition to simplifying the process and building joint skills and confidence in forecasts (with the traffic light system being a good approach), a challenge is that forecasts are often presented in terms of probabilities. This can lead to misunderstandings, where higher probabilities are interpreted as certainties ("it will happen"), and when the forecast doesn't come true, it undermines confidence in the product. This leads back to discussion about evaluating the long-term value of predictions, particularly in terms of economic value. However, to assess this, data on costs and losses from the relevant sector is needed.

3.4. Summary of Workshop

Engagement with NMSs is crucial for advancing and applying ASPECT outputs. Therefore, a two-day online Workshop was organized to foster collaboration between ASPECT and NMSs. The event aimed to enhance communication, showcase ASPECT research, gather feedback, and establish channels for sharing climate prediction data. It also laid the foundation for scaling climate information and enhancing its application.

The Workshop focused on operational and innovative seasonal-to-decadal predictions, predictability research, novel approaches and user needs. It featured a set of presentations and extensive discussions.

The knowledge, experience and ideas shared can be summarized as the following:

1. Climate projections are more widely used than initialized predictions, likely because they have been developed and refined over several decades resulting in practical and accessible products. On the other hand, initialized predictions are newer, less mature, and more complex, requiring specialized knowledge to interpret.
2. Subseasonal-to-seasonal (S2S) predictions, addressing the forecasting range from weeks to two months, are essential for Climate Watch Advisories. Although ASPECT does not directly cover S2S forecasts, they are recognized as a gap that needs bridging. ECMWF is working on enhancing S2S predictions and making S2S data accessible in real time. **Looking ahead, there is interest in exploring further research opportunities to connect sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, potentially through EU-funded projects.**
3. **Assessing the value of initialization in climate predictions is important.** Ideally, such assessments should be done annually for each initialization, though this can be challenging for users.

While some suggest focusing on the value predictions offer rather than forecast skill, there is uncertainty about whether the relatively modest added value from initialization is enough to improve decision-making. When this value is limited, co-production with users becomes important to increase the usefulness of predictions through context-specific information.

4. Initialized simulations are also valuable for verifying significant changes in Earth's systems like the loss of Arctic sea ice or changes in the AMOC. By capturing variability more effectively, these predictions offer a clearer view of changes expected over the next 10–20 years.
5. Teleconnections are essential for climate predictions. However, global warming may disrupt these patterns, reducing the reliability of historical relationships. Models often struggle to accurately replicate observed variability. The influence of teleconnections depends on the timescale, and the source of predictability may vary accordingly. **While models generally simulate ENSO well, other modes of variability and their interactions remain areas for further research.**

6. With climate change leading to more frequent and unprecedented extremes, predictions have become essential in evaluating the likelihood of unusual events that fall outside historical expectations. Climate predictions also offer insights into the changing distribution of climate conditions over time.
7. A research suggestion was made to **explore whether it is possible to identify weather patterns or larger-scale modes of variability linked to an increase in extreme rainfall from convective events.**
8. Event attribution, which examines the causes of specific extreme events, is a key aspect of the attribution challenge and its credibility is enhanced by using the initialized models.
9. Models face challenges in accurately representing key processes and teleconnections, as well as with biases, leading to weak predictable signals. **Addressing model deficiencies, such as signal-to-noise issues and predictable components, is crucial.**

The potential predictability in nature is not fully captured by models which result in diverse circulation patterns in seasonal predictions, minimal variance in predicted signals and low predictive skill. Current bias correction methods, often relying on climatology, do not fully **eliminate non-stationary biases**, prompting the exploration of more advanced techniques like machine learning. Another challenge is **correcting trend biases** in climate predictions, due to complex model physics and long-standing deficiencies. Trend-related errors, in particular, compromise the usefulness of predictions in the current climate. While calibration is used as an interim solution, the ideal fix is to address model deficiencies.

10. Downscaling is necessary for adapting climate predictions to high-resolution applications needed by users. **The effectiveness of downscaling techniques depends on the quality, resolution, and length of available observational data for training and calibration.** For statistical downscaling, the limited availability of certain variables, like those at pressure levels, restricts the use of more advanced techniques. Analog downscaling methods could improve predictive skill if biases in circulation patterns are rigorously corrected across spatial and temporal dimensions.
11. Machine learning and AI are seen as a promising tool for bias correction and generating high-resolution predictions. However, **testing new methods is difficult due to the limited high-quality observational data, as well as number of cases and initialization dates of traditional simulations.** Testing and feedback on new methods require time and larger datasets to ensure robustness, particularly as climate change adds new complexities.
12. **Many users are often unaware of, struggle to understand or have difficulty distinguishing between interannual climate predictions and long-term projections.** This highlights the need for better communication and education.

Miscommunication and a lack of alignment between user needs and available data make it difficult to apply initialized predictions broadly. Additionally, the scientific and user communities tend to favor projections.

13. Climate information should be customized to address specific user needs and expert support provided. **Users prioritize credibility, clarity, and relevance over the source of the data, whether it comes from predictions or projections.** Effective use of climate predictions demands extensive interaction, training, and patience from users, especially when benefits are marginal compared to other data sources.
14. Sustained engagement with users is crucial but resource-intensive, particularly for National Meteorological Services (NMSs) with limited capacity. **Many services and tools start as prototypes funded by research projects, and maintaining and transitioning them into operational practice is challenging.**
15. Users may not always express their requirements clearly from the start, so existing tools can help identify gaps and spark discussions. **Interactive and ongoing engagement with users** encourages mutual learning, can help simplify the processes, build joint skills, and increase confidence in forecasts.
16. **A profitable market for climate services is hard to identify**, making it difficult to pool resources and raise the visibility of the issue. There is also a lack of mechanisms to provide resources to National Meteorological Services (NMSs) to channel research developments into society. **Translating predictions into tangible value, like economic savings**, can help drive adoption and build trust in climate services. To maximize impact, probabilistic data should be framed within the **cost-benefit contexts** of various sectors.
17. Unlike traditional meteorology, in which formal training programs are available, there is a **gap in education for interpreting and communicating seasonal and climate predictions.**

3.5. Analysis of number of participants

An analysis of the number of participants was conducted, both in total numbers (Table 2) and by geographical distribution (Figures 4-8).

There were 179 registered participants from 44 different countries, of which 146 were participants from NMSs (participants from the research institutions that are project partners were excluded⁶). We managed to attract at least one person from nearly all European countries, except for 6. There was good representation of the Middle East and Caucasus, as well as some African countries. The highest number of registered participants from NMSs came from the UK (20), Azerbaijan (13) and Romania (11).

In total, 149 people participated in the event, i.e. 118 without research partners. 62 participants from NMSs attended the Workshop on both days. Four countries, among those registered, didn't have representatives (Iceland, Jordan, Lebanon, Montenegro). The countries with the most representation were UK (16), Azerbaijan (12), Romania (8) and Serbia (8).

Table 2 Number of countries and participants per different categories.

	Number of countries (with research project partners)	Number of participants (with research project partners)	Number of countries (without research project partners)	Number of participants (without research project partners)	Participants from research project partners
Number of registered participants	44	179	44	146	33
Number of participants - total	40	149	40	118	31
Number of participants - day 1	38	128	38	99	29
Number of participants - day 2	34	106	34	81	25

⁶ Excluded institutions from the analysis: BSC, CMCC, ECMWF, Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, University of Oxford, University of Leeds.

Table 3 shows the average time of participation. Participants attended the event for an average of ~2 hours, with slightly more interest in the content of Day2.

Table 3 Average time of participation.

	Average time in the session (with research project partners)	Average time in the session (without research project partners)
Total	1.99 hours	1.93 hours
Day 1	1.93 hours	1.86 hours
Day 2	2.05 hours	2.02 hours

Figure 4 Number of registered participants - left with, right without participants from the research institutions participating in ASPECT

Figure 5 Total number of participants - left with, right without participants from the research institutions participating in ASPECT

The first day had more participants than the second, (128 vs. 106), and more represented countries (38 vs. 34). Looking at the number of participants from NMSs, there were 99 on the first day, and 18 participants fewer on the second.

On the first day, the most represented countries from NMSs were UK (12), Azerbaijan (11), and Serbia (8), while on the second day UK (11), Serbia (8) and Romania (6). There were more African countries represented on the second day.

Figure 6 Number of participants at day 1 - left with, right without participants from the research institutions participating in ASPECT

Figure 7 Number of participants at day 2 - left with, right without participants from the research institutions participating in ASPECT

Figure 8 Number of registered but not showed up

3.6. Post workshop activities

3.6.1. Evaluation

The impressions on the Workshop were collected during and after the Workshop via an Evaluation Form.

The Form was filled out by 17 participants, who rated the content of the Workshop and presentations on average of 4.2 on a scale of 1 to 5.

The speakers were praised for their engagement. There were suggestions that more attention should be given to the user perspective, even when discussing the development of S2D prediction systems (modeling part).

Participants expressed interest in attending future ASPECT events and provided some suggestions for future topics. They would like to:

- see new developments, improvements and progress done in the ASPECT;
- have practical training on how to use products operationally and how to produce custom-made products based on ASPECT forecasts;
- learn more on high-resolution climate models;
- learn more on S2S forecast.

Detailed feedback and suggestions for the future events can be found in Appendix III.

Positive feedback on the Workshop for NMSs was shared by its speakers and panellists during the WMO RA VI RCC User Forum and RA VI RCC Coordination Team meeting, held in November 2024. The need for decadal predictions, as expressed by NMSs, was emphasized, highlighting the importance of the ASPECT project in providing valuable information.

3.6.2. Sharing Workshop material

After the workshop, a news article about the Workshop was created and posted on the ASPECT webpage and social media (X and LinkedIn). Presentations that were agreed to be public were published on the website⁷, while its recordings will be available at the beginning of the 2025. The recording of the entire Workshop will be available internally for project partners on ASPECT wiki.

Workshop materials were shared with all registered participants along with the link to the questionnaire for gathering information for WP1 and WP6. This way, those who couldn't participate had a chance to see the presentations on ASPECT activities and take part in the survey.

Additionally, the mailing list was expanded by ~75 contacts from those who expressed interest in being informed about ASPECT activities.

⁷ <https://www.aspect-project.eu/from-seasons-to-decades-a-workshop-for-national-meteorological-services/>

4. Further engagement with National Meteorological Services

Operational weather and climate forecasters and climate services providers are one of the key target groups for all CDE activities in ASPECT.

ASPECT plans to work with up to 10 NMSs, leveraging their role in delivering weather and climate information to embed ASPECT's advancements into operational workflows. This engagement will involve consultations to address specific needs and challenges, fostering adoption of new data and methodologies. The NMSs will be selected in a way to maximise uptake, satisfy demand, and achieve geographical coverage.

During the Workshop discussions, questionnaires conducted with NMSs, internal ASPECT webinars and consultations, and other events, the need for education of NMSs staff and end users was emphasized. ASPECT will prepare training programs to ensure the effective application of improved prediction models and workflows. This can be achieved in several ways:

- utilizing existing channels to educate NMS staff, such as organizing training events within MedCOF or making training materials available on the EUMeTrain webpage⁸.
- creating educational materials to be shared on the ASPECT webpage and promoting them during the User Forums organized by ASPECT.

Better outreach, accessibility and engagement of educational and promotional material could be achieved by creating multilingual material.

Working closely with the WMO and other international organizations to leverage their networks can help identifying and engaging diverse experts, as well as sharing lessons learned and outputs. This will also ensure a contribution to the maintenance and enhancement of the WMO Lead Centre on Annual to Decadal Prediction. Cooperation with RCOFs can be effectively expanded to meet the needs of developing and disseminating regional products.

Exploring novel approaches and technologies, as well as the impacts of climate change on weather patterns and extreme events, highlights the need for high-resolution and high-quality observational data. Emphasizing this need can help secure funding to strengthen the capacities of NMSs. Additional resources are also required to support the operationalization of created prototypes and to establish channels for translating research developments into societal benefits.

ASPECT actively promotes gender inclusivity by reaching out to female experts in the field during the planning stages of events. However, further efforts are needed to enhance the geographical representation of ASPECT output users. Outreach to underrepresented regions, particularly Eastern Europe, could be strengthened by engaging directly with NMSs in these areas to identify their experts

⁸ <https://www.eumetrain.org/>

and build relationships. Additionally, ASPECT can provide support to these NMSs to help them develop their climate services effectively.

ANNEX I Leaflet with Agenda

22 and 23 October 2024
13:30-16:00 CEST, online

Workshop for National Meteorological Services

FROM SEASONS TO DECADES: SEAMLESS PREDICTION FOR A BETTER FUTURE

ASPECT is inviting you to join us for an exciting workshop showcasing cutting-edge climate forecasts.

ASPECT is a Horizon Europe project investigating seamless climate predictions that cover timescales from seasonal to multi-decadal. The project is working closely with users from several sectors to ensure that these forecasts cover their current and future information needs.

In this workshop, we will explore new forecasting horizons and emphasize the added value of initialization in climate predictions. While highlighting these advancements, we will also discuss the limitations of state-of-the-art multi-system predictions, all from the perspectives of providers and users.

Day 1 is focused on production and provision of operational and innovative seasonal-to-decadal predictions. We will introduce and discuss protocols for providing climate information and efforts on how to make data FAIR as well as discuss the challenges of working with various archiving infrastructures.

Day 2 will call attention to current multi-system predictions and the added value of initialization, while also addressing their limitations, such as unrealistic extremes and the signal-to-noise issue. We will delve into the latest methods for temporal merging and downscaling, designed to deliver high-resolution, user-specific information across multiple time scales. Collaborative case studies will be presented to showcase the power of tailored climate information in supporting better-informed adaptation decisions. We will also go beyond individual case studies and explore user needs as well as the drivers of climate risk management and climate information use in Europe.

22 and 23 October 2024
13:30–16:00 CEST, online

DAY 1 - 22 OCTOBER

- 13:30 Welcome & Introduction to workshop
- 13:40 Introduction to the ASPECT project, *Albert Soret (BSC)*

Session 1: Seasonal to Decadal predictions

- 13:55 Operational predictions and exciting developments of seasonal to decadal predictions at the Met Office in the UK, *Leon Hermanson (Met Office)*
- 14:10 Current and future climate prediction systems at DWD (German Meteorological Service), *Kristina Fröhlich (DWD)*
- 14:25 *Coffee Break*
- 14:35 Novel configurations of prediction systems for seamless climate information *Magdalena Alonso Balmaseda (ECMWF)*
- 14:55 ASPECT data management: guidelines and documentation *Chiara Cagnazzo and Charalampos Karvelis (ECMWF)*
- 15:10 **Roundtable & Discussion**
Francisco Doblas-Reyes (BSC), Pasha Karami (SMHI), Dario Nicolli (CMCC), Esteban Rodríguez Guisado (MedCOF, AEMET)
- 16:00 **Wrap-up**

DAY 2 - 23 OCTOBER

- 13:30 Welcome & Introduction to day 2

Session 2: Predictability & Novel approaches

- 13:35 Perspectives from RCC-LRF co-lead on seasonal forecasting over RA-VI Europe *Lauriane Batté (Météo-France)*
- 13:50 Opportunities and challenges of seasonal-to-decadal climate predictions of European mean climate and extremes, *Holger Pohlmann (MPG | MPI-M)*
- 14:05 What can novel approaches towards seamless climate information further add to climate services?, *Beena Balan Sarojini (University of Oxford)*
- 14:20 **Roundtable & Discussion**
Clementine Dalelane (DWD), Philip Lorenz (DWD), Ramon Fuentes-Franco (SMHI)
- 14:50 *Coffee Break*

Session 3: User needs

- 15:00 Co-development of case studies with Super Users, *Verónica Torralba (BSC)*
- 15:15 Climate information use in Europe, *Suraje Dessai (University of Leeds)*
- 15:30 **Roundtable & Discussion**
Ralf Doescher (SMHI), Freya Garry (Met Office), Amelie Hoff (DWD)
- 16:00 **Wrap-up**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101011462.

ANNEX II Invitation letter

Dear colleagues,

I am writing to you on behalf of the Horizon Europe project [ASPECT](#). The project aims to improve and produce seamless climate predictions covering the next 30 years, while also working closely with stakeholders from several sectors.

We would like to invite you to our **workshop “From seasons to decades: seamless prediction for a better future”**, which will take place on **22 and 23 October 2024**, from 13:30 to 16:00 CEST, **Online**.

This workshop is **dedicated to national and regional Meteorological Services**. It will explore advances on the road towards seamless climate predictions and discuss the limitations of state-of-the-art multi-system predictions, all from the perspectives of information providers and users. The workshop will enable the exchange of knowledge, ideas, experiences and needs between Meteorological Services and ASPECT researchers.

The sessions will focus on three main topics:

1. Seasonal to decadal predictions;
2. Predictability and novel approaches in modelling (e.g., prediction of extreme events, high-resolution downscaling and temporal merging); and
3. User needs regarding long range predictions.

You can find more information and the Agenda in the attachment.

To participate in the workshop, please **register [HERE](#)**.

Please, feel free to forward this invitation to any colleagues who might be interested.

Kind regards,
Aleksandra Krzic
Republic Hydrometeorological Service of Serbia - RHMZ
ASPECT project partner

ANNEX III Participants responses in evaluation

Table A1 Please provide any feedback or comments for the workshop
Sometimes it got quite technical on the first day for someone who works on the 'human side,' I am looking forward to the part on co-development tomorrow
Well organised and efficient
Day 1 answer so I'll wait for Day 2 but I found discussions could have more included a user perspective even in Day 1 :)
useful informations, thanks
its a big joy to attend such level of expertise and profesionality, thank YOU!
Thank you it were very useful
All speakers were as engaging

Table A2 Let us know if you would like to join future workshops and what you would like to see
Yes
I would like to keep participating
Information on progress made and also on the possible uptake by targeted users
S2S forecast
I would like to join and see an improvement regarding the most important things
high-resolution climate models
training on how to use products operationally and how to produce custom-made products based on your forecasts

Yes i would like to join and I hope there is Practical training
new development of the system at future workshops